

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D 1.1 Structure and members of the Driving Group, Community of Schools and National Coordinators' Board

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
project number 101059425

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement of the project 101059425. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DELIVERABLE ID

Deliverable No.	D1.1	Work Package No.	WP1	Task/s No.	Task 1.1 – 1.2
Work Package Title	LET'S CARE: Building up a community				
Linked Task/s Title	T1.1. Driving Group conformation and management T1.2. Build a community of schools: LET'S CARE CoS				
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, SEN-Sensitive)			
Due date deliverable	2023-01-31	Submission date	2023-02-28		
Deliverable name	Structure and members of the Driving Group, Community of Schools and National Coordinators' Board				

DOCUMENT CONTRIBUTORS

Deliverable responsible	2. CID	
Contributors	Organisation	
NURIA LORES	CIDALIA	
STEFANO COBELLO	POLO	
Reviewers	Organisation	
ALBA COUSO	COMILLAS	
AMAIA HALTY	COMILLAS	
EVA BAJO MARCOS	COMILLAS	
ABEL MUÑIZ	ZIC	
CAROLINA SIMÓN	ZIC	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	2023-01-15	First Draft of the document
0.2	2023-02-13	Second Draft of the document
0.3	2023-02-24	Third Draft of the document
0.4	2023-02-28	Final document

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Executive Summary	5
2. Introduction.....	6
3. Driving Group (DG)	7
3.1. Structure and composition	7
3.2. Main tasks	9
4. National Coordinators' Board (NCB)	9
4.1. NCB Structure and composition.....	9
4.2. Main tasks of the National Coordinators' Board	10
5. Let's Care Community of Schools (CoS).....	11
5.1. CoS Structure and composition.....	11
5.1.1. CoS building strategy	11
5.1.2. CoS actual composition.....	14
5.2. Main tasks of the CoS.....	19
Annex I: CoS Recruitment Fact Sheet	21

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CoS	Community of Schools
DG	Driving Group
NCB	National Coordinators' Board
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
GDC	Gender and Diversity committee
HUB	On-line platform

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. DG members	8
Table 2. NCB current members	10
Table 3. Community of schools (CoS) members.....	18

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Summary of the LET'S CARE Communities	6
Figure 2. CoS building phases	13

1. Executive Summary

The document presents the different structures foreseen in the LET'S CARE community-building project. A brief presentation of each of them has been included, as well as the commitments they should have and their added value. The specific composition of the members of the Driving Group (DG) and the Community of Schools (CoS) is also set out in the document.

2. Introduction

The Let's Care project seeks to link research, technological development and community innovation to understand how a safe attachment can positively affect early school leaving (ESL) and educational (under)achievement in Europe and improve the caring dimension of education systems. The following sections develop specifically on the community building strategy implemented to guarantee this multi-partner approach, how the links and coordination with the Let's Care community are defined and the final conformation, structure and roles of the actors involved.

A **Driving Group (DG)**, a **Community of Schools (CoS)** and a **National Coordinator's Board (NCB)** will be the key groups of actors involved. The continuous communication of these actors will contribute to elaborate a definition of a safe education model that acknowledges the real educational experiences of teachers and students and provides a bottom-up perspective of the caring aspects related to ESL and educational (under)achievement. Additionally, these actors will help to establish the community and institutional context to enable the data collection and analysis; the development and diagnosis of intervention tools; and the advocacy, awareness and incidence activities of the project.

Figure 1. Summary of the LET'S CARE Communities

3. Driving Group (DG)

The **Driving Group (DG)** is a body made up of one representative from each project partner to dynamise all the project's tasks and activities and link the consortium vision with the rest of the communities, co-constructing and engaging with all the other relevant actors. Its most important functions are coordinating and articulating the National Coordinators' Board (NCB) and the Community of Schools (CoS), whose main functions are explained below. The DG will also operationalise the Policy Maker Advisory Board (PMAB), facilitating contact with other policy-makers at the national, regional and European levels. In addition, this body will be responsible for ensuring a Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology. The representativeness of all partners will guarantee a fieldwork with multi-stakeholder vision.

3.1. Structure and composition

The project proposal established that the Driving Group (DG) should be composed of at least one representative member per project partner. Accordingly, the DG is currently composed of 23 members: 14 are full members, and additionally, 9 substitutes have been appointed to ensure and facilitate the participation of the different entities in the DG. The full members constitute a gender-balanced group composed of 7 women and 7 men. Including the additional 9 substitutes, the full group of 23 members is composed of 14 women and 9 men. Table 1 shows the members of the DG. After the official formation of the DG, it was agreed that the group would virtually convene each 4-6 months to provide strategic inputs for all project activities, supported and dynamised by a Technical Secretary led by CIDALIA. From the beginning of the project to the present (M5), the DG has met on 12 December 2022 and 7 February 2023. The DG can be a regular and frequent meeting place for all partners focusing on all issues related to WP1.

D 1.1 Structure and members of the DG, CoS and NCB

Nº	PARTNER	NAME/SURNAME TITULAR	NAME/SURNAME SUBSTITUTE
1	COMILLAS	A.Halty	A.Couso
2	CIDALIA	N.Lores	J.Migallón
3	FACHHOCHSCHULE VORARLBERG GMBH (FHV)	F.Maurer	R.Sifferlinger
4	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO DI BOSCOCHIESANUOVA (POLO)	S.Cobello	E.Milli
5	Fundación Promaestro	J.Úbeda	M.Verástegui
6	TIMELEX	P.Gryffroy	O.Barda
7	CONSEJERIA DE EDUCACIÓN Y EMPLEO - JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA	J.F.Fuella Moreno	C.Murillo Gómez
8	STOWARZYSZENIE ARID	M.Dymacz	
9	PANEVEZIO RAJONO SVIETIMO CENTRAS (PRSC)	I.Žilinskienė	
10	ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING, S.A.	C.Simón	
11	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA (UCP)	P.Días	
12	Akademia Ignatianum Krakowie	E.Dybowska	E.Sowa-Behtane
13	STICHTING INTERNATIONAL PARENTS ALLIANCE (IPA)	E.Salamon	L.Janka László
14	KITE	I.Aleksandrova Angelova	

Table 1. DG members

3.2. Main tasks

The DG holds the essential task of sharing the project's values with key stakeholders and actors that belong to the LET'S CARE communities, thus taking care of:

- To be a space for participation and decision-making of all the partners about the different community structures of the project.
- To provide strategic inputs for all project activities.
- To incorporate the inputs from CoS representatives and the NCB.
- To be trained in PAR methodology and to be responsible for the implementation of this methodology in all project activities.

4. National Coordinators' Board (NCB)

A **National Coordinators' Board (NCB)** will be progressively created with 2 coordinators per country to ensure effective communication and coordination with the DG. The main function of this body is to facilitate the fieldwork tasks and develop meaningful relationships between the fieldwork partners and the participants of the Let's Care Communities. During M6-12, NCB will define characteristics, select and invite up to 120 educational centres (20/country), where quantitative data collection will be implemented, becoming part of the LET'S CARE CoS and being invited to participate in LET'S CARE Hub.

4.1. NCB Structure and composition

The National Coordinators' Board (NCB) facilitates, coordinates and guides the activities of the CoS empowering stakeholders and giving them management and decision-making capacity. It represents a direct link between the Consortium and the CoS. The NCB is composed of:

- a) A representative of each fieldwork project partner responsible for the pilots in the schools.
- b) A representative of the local/national schools' network for each country. This member can represent public or private organisations or networks impacting several schools and institutions.

The partners select the representatives of the schools' networks according to a few requirements that will enable the project implementation, including:

- Sharing of project values.
- Experience in the educational and research field.
- Commitment to the project's successful implementation.
- Knowledge of the English language.
- Availability to participate in local and European meetings.

The NCB must be a stable reference point at the national level throughout the whole duration of the project and after its conclusion.

The Board is elected every four years. The first representatives are the members of the consortium and the identified teachers, but in the following years, the members will be the expression of the will of the members of each nation.

The NCB has already started to be set up and has all its representative members of each project partner. During the following months the representative of the local/national schools' network for each country will join. The NCB composition will be finalized for M16. The current members are:

Nº	PARTNER	NAME/SURNAME
1	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO DI BOSCOCHIESANUOVA (POLO)	S.Cobello
2	CONSEJERIA DE EDUCACIÓN Y EMPLEO - JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA	J.F.Fuella Moreno
3	STOWARZYSZENIE ARID	M.Dymacz
4	PANEVEZIO RAJONO SVIETIMO CENTRAS (PRSC)	I.Žilinskienė
5	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA (UCP)	P.Días
6	KITE	I.Aleksandrova Angelova

Table 2. NCB current members

4.2. Main tasks of the National Coordinators' Board

The main task of the NCB will be:

- Debate, discuss and overview CoS's tasks such as adaptation of data collection instruments, local adjustments of sampling decisions, PAR methodology implementation, contextual validation of language and translation, etc.
- Set up the most appropriate communication channels with the adherent schools (news, announcements, newsletters, integration with face-to-face meetings, etc.).
- Define characteristics, select and invite new schools to join the Community to contribute to the quantitative data collection.
- Support the members of the CoS, promote and sponsor local/national/European events or seminars and workshops about Safe Education.
- Represent a contact point for the members of the Community at national level.
- Propose further research within the project's subject.

5. Let's Care Community of Schools (CoS)

LET'S CARE **Community of Schools (CoS)** is a real and virtual network in which the principles of the Safe Education approach are transmitted, implemented and validated through the involvement of teachers, principals, schools and educational institutions. The Safe Education approach developed by LET'S CARE focuses on improving the caring dimension of education to overcome the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion. The Community of Schools creates a European-wide link between teachers who share a common understanding of the importance of preventing exclusion, underachievement, disengagement and school dropout by the creation of a safe educational environment for all learners.

The CoS is the backbone of the project and its implementation in educational environments will actively contribute to providing data and co-construct a wider view and narratives for the design and implementation of the project's activities.

5.1. CoS Structure and composition

LET'S CARE Community of Schools (CoS) will be formed in 2 main phases. Initially, CoS will be composed of 3 schools from the fieldwork countries (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Bulgaria, Poland and Lithuania). That is called "the seed of the LET'S CARE CoS". In a second phase, the CoS will be expanded to 120 members (at least 20 schools per country, considering the 6 States previously mentioned). By the year 2028, the involvement of schools from other countries in the community of interest could be expected through collaboration with other community networks that share CoS values (e.g. "Nobody Less"¹).

5.1.1. CoS building strategy

The building up of the Community of Schools (CoS) is a process that will be implemented in 3 phases:

1) Community of interest: in the first phase of the project, partners will present LET'S CARE project and its aims to several stakeholders. School directors and teachers will inform the partners about their interest in joining the network. This initial group of schools will be introduced to the Safe Education approach and LET'S CARE tools in order to provide them with a clearer understanding of the commitment required by the Community. The Community of Interest is not only composed by

¹Nobody Less is a network of stakeholders (schools, NGOs, etc.) working together for prosocial values. The network was built inside a European project. For more information: <https://nobodyless.org/>

teachers but also by people interested in the results of the project as stakeholders, professors, researchers, doctors, practitioners in the field of education and psychology, decision-makers, policymakers or representatives of associations and organizations. The community of interest is an online space open to discussing about the project's topics. General information about the project and its results will be shared in the community through a mailing list or/and chats. The community of interest will support the implementation of the project since it will:

- Contribute to the dissemination of the project.
- Identify participating / piloting schools.
- Engage target groups through discussions and exchanges of opinions.
- Enrich the feedback and the contributions to the Safe Education approach adaptation to the educational context.
- Facilitate the engagement of the members in the Network of Stakeholders.
- Ease the participation of target group from non-partner countries.

2) Initial Community of Schools (the seed of the CoS): each of the 6 partners involved in the project's piloting phase has to select within the community of interest 3 schools/country (18 in total) that will represent the initial core of the CoS. These schools will be directly involved in the project's model validation, qualitative data collection and piloting phases. Teachers and principals of these schools will be trained in Participatory Action Research and Let's Care methodologies. The project piloting partners will try to involve a school of every level of education (pre-school, primary and secondary) whenever it will be possible.

3) Wider Community of Schools: in a following phase, project's partners with the support of the National Coordinators Board (NCB), will select new schools for a total of 20 schools per country (120 in total). These schools will be involved and included in the quantitative data collection.

Figure 2. CoS building phases

So as to complete different phases, the figure of “**Reference Teachers**” might be necessary. They are going to be motivated, dynamic teachers that serve as nodes for the Community in their local context. They will be the main contact people for the school in the relation with NCB, the CoS and the local community (i.e. other schools interested). These teachers are committed to supporting their colleagues in the implementation of the Safe Education approach. By joining the community, teachers have the opportunity to access educational materials related to LET’S CARE, share best practices, questions, thoughts, ideas and inspiration with colleagues from all around Europe, propose topics for discussion; additionally, they are able to get advice on how to design Safe Education activities. They will be the first addressees of some trainings and events related to LET’S CARE. Through these courses and direct contact with other CoS members and the NCB these teachers will, on their turn, train their colleagues in the use of Safe Teaching and Participatory Action Research.

The tasks of the Reference Teachers will be:

- Participate in some training courses organized by the project’s partners.
- Keep the NCB representatives informed about the activities in their schools.
- Facilitate the data collection in their schools.
- Involve their colleagues in training and piloting moments.
- Share good practices related to the project.
- Be active in the LET’S CARE HUB.
- Facilitate the involvement of the families and the local community.

The advantages of being a Reference Teacher will be:

- Receive specific training on Safe Teaching and Participatory Action Research (PAR) to improve the academic results and inclusion of all the students.
- Improve their professional competences and skills.
- Be part of the collaborative dynamic of self and peer observation.
- Access to good educational practices.
- Have access to experimental tools useful for school guidance.

The selection of the Reference Teachers will be made without discrimination of any kind, and every effort will be made to respect gender and diversity perspectives.

5.1.2. CoS actual composition

Following the planning of the Let's Care project, the seed of the CoS has been set up. As can be seen in Table 3, nowadays, CoS is composed of 19 schools (one more than the minimum initially planned). However, Portugal has so far only managed to secure the commitment of two schools instead of three. Public schools in Portugal are currently experiencing a complicated situation with a very difficult conflict between teachers and the Ministry of Education. This is manifested in strikes almost every week and protests in different cities. As a result, public schools are refusing to collaborate on new projects because teachers are overwhelmed by administrative tasks, among other reasons for protest. The Portuguese partner is working on the recruitment for the third school in Portugal.

The composition of the seed of the CoS is heterogeneous according to the variables established:

- Educational Level (Primary, Secondary, etc.)
- Geographical situation (urban, countryside, outside a big city).
- Presence of disadvantaged populations (ethnicity, especially Roma children, migrant background, SES, (dis)ability; (non)parental care).

In the next months, LET'S CARE project will be working on the second phase to build a wider community composed of 120 schools (20/ piloting country).

D 1.1 Structure and members of the DG, CoS and NCB

PERSON'S POSITION	NAME OF THE SCHOOL	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	COUNTRY	GEOGRAPHICAL SITUATION	DISADVANTAGED POPULATIONS ¹	WEBSITE
Director	Zespół Szkół i Placówek Specjalnych w Krakowie	Primary	Poland	Urban	Light disability and social problems	www.kr.edu.pl
Director	Szkoła podstawowa w Pstroszycach Pierwszych	Primary	Poland	Rural	No disadvantages	www.sppstroszyc.e.pl
Director	Zespół Szkół Secjalnych nr 4 w Krakowie	Primary and secondary	Poland	Urban	Deep disabilities	http://www.zss4krakow.pl/
Director	I Liceum Ogólnokształcące w Limanowej	High school	Poland	Urban Small City	No disadvantages	https://www.1lo.limanowa.pl/
Director	Municipal School "St.St. Kiril Methodi" -Malorad vilage, Bororvan Municipality	Middle school	Bulgaria	Rural	Disadvantage/ethnicity Vlachs	https://ou-kirilimetodii.eu/
Director	Municipal School "Vasil Levski" - Shumata vilage	Middle school	Bulgaria	Rural	Disadvantage/ethnicity ROMA	https://www.ou-schumata.com/
Director	Municipal School "Stephen Peshev" - Sevlievo	Middle school	Bulgaria	Urban Small City	Disadvantage/SES	ou2_sevlievo@abv.bg

D 1.1 Structure and members of the DG, CoS and NCB

Reference teacher	Municipality School "St.Paisii Hilendarski" - Kyustendil	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	Disadvantage/ethnicity ROMA /non parental	https://6ou.info/
Reference teacher	I.C. Isola della Scala	Pre-primary to Middle school	Italy	Rural	All disadvantages	https://www.istitutocomprendivoisola.edu.it/
Reference teacher	I.C. Bosco Chiesanuova	Pre-primary to Middle school	Italy	Mountains	All disadvantages	https://www.istitutobosco.edu.it/
Reference teacher	I.C. 06 Chievo Bassona	Pre-primary to Middle school	Italy	Mixed urban and rural	All disadvantages	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
English teacher European project expert teacher	IES Reino Aftasí CEIP Francisco Montero de Espinosa	Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education.	Spain	Urban. Schooling of rural students in non-compulsory levels	All disadvantages	https://reinoaftasi.es/
English teacher European	CEIP Francisco Montero de Espinosa	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban Small City	All disadvantages	https://cpfmespinosa.educarex.es/

projects expert teacher						
Guidance teacher. Member of the management team	COL Virgen de Guadalupe- Fundación Loyola	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education. Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education.	Spain	Urban. Schooling of rural students in non-compulsory levels	All disadvantages	https://fundacionloyola.com/vguadalupe/
English teacher	Panevėžio „Šaltinio“ Progimnazija	Pre-primary to Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	All disadvantages	https://saltinioprogramnazija.lt/
Director	Panevėžio r. Raguvos Gimnazija	Pre-primary to Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	All disadvantages	https://raguvosgimnazija.lt/
Director	Panevėžio r. Naujamiesčio Mokykla	Pre-primary to Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	All disadvantages	https://nvmokykla.lt/
Director	Colégio de Nossa Senhora do Rosário	Pre-primary to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	No disadvantages	https://www.colegiodorosario.pt/

D 1.1 Structure and members of the DG, CoS and NCB

English teacher	Agrupamento de Escolas Dr. Manuel Laranjeira	Primary to Secondary School	Portugal	Mixed urban and rural	No specific disadvantages	https://www.aem.laranjeira.pt/
-----------------	--	-----------------------------	----------	-----------------------	---------------------------	---

Notes. 1 Disadvantaged populations based on ethnicity (especially roma children), migrant background, socio-economic status, (dis)ability; (non)parental care

Table 3. Community of schools (CoS) members

5.2. Main tasks of the CoS

The schools in the community will represent different:

- educational levels (pre-school, primary, secondary (general and vocational), second chance education centres),
- contexts (rural, urban),
- school ownership (public, private).

Partners will preferably select schools with ethnic, social and linguistic diversity thus to ensure the presence of students with fewer opportunities (geographical, social, cultural, economic situations), students with migrant background, and students with difficulties and special educational needs.

The schools that will be part of the community must ensure continuity in participation through a written agreement with the consortium. The members of the CoS will be considered Pole-schools that will inform other schools in their territory about Safe Education. They will organize or host dissemination events or trainings for other teachers.

The advantages of being part of school in the CoS will be:

- Receive specific training on Safe Teaching and Participatory Action Research to improve the academic results and inclusion of all the students.
- Improve the well-being and the inclusion of the students.
- Understand the dynamics of successful academic results and reduce the drop-out rates.
- Improve teachers' competences, knowledge, skills and motivation, especially about the needs of learners with difficulties and at risk of social and educational exclusion.
- Belonging to a network of support and exchange of safe educational practices.
- Bring prestige to the school by assuming an important social value as innovators.
- Implement new educational strategies and good practices.
- Implement and take advantage of the direct results of the piloting phase.
- Strengthen the collaboration among schools and institutions at the European level.
- Be able to develop, promote and encourage the implementation of quality, sustainable and inclusive educational practices, projects and activities.
- Be involved in dialogue, reflection, cooperation and innovation in the educational field.

Commitments of the CoS members will be:

- Participate in the specific training on PAR and LET'S CARE methodology.
- Participate in the qualitative data collection (initial seed of the CoS).
- Participate in the quantitative data collection.
- Participate in information meetings, training courses online and in presence.
- Be active in the Let's Care HUB.
- Be in active communication with the other members of the CoS, promoting dialogue and discussion.
- Involve families of the students.
- Involve all the teachers at the school (or at least the 3/4 of them).
- Pilot Safe Education approach.
- Organize/host training events for other schools in the territory.
- Promote and support research, innovation, application and development of methodologies for Safe Education and inclusive teaching.
- Encourage exchanges, dissemination of good practices and all activities aimed at improving inclusive and Safe education.
- Engage the local community in understanding the importance of the Safe Education to tackle the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion.

Annex I: CoS Recruitment Fact Sheet

LET'S CARE

EC - PROJECT NUMBER: 101059425

WP1: LET'S CARE: BUILDING UP A COMMUNITY

COMMUNITY OF SCHOOLS (CoS)

Secure attachment relationships play an important protective role against the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion, not only at early stages, but at all school levels. LET'S CARE aims to comprehensively understand and improve the caring dimension of educational inclusion and school success.

The project main objective is to identify determinants affecting student security as a root cause of underachievement, disengagement and school dropout, at 4 different ecological levels: individual, relational, community and political. LET'S CARE will create a theoretical and practical framework to foster Safe Learning, Safe Teaching, Safe Schools and Safe Education in each level as an approach to break the chain of transgenerational transmission of educational and social exclusion. This approach will generate lower rates of school failure, poor learning outcomes and early school leaving.

The main proposal breakthrough is based on considering a relational response to educational exclusion and inequality, resulting in a model for understanding the importance of security to address underachievement and early dropout, and a relational approach to inclusive practices at school that will be translated into tools, recommendations and guidelines for action, from ECEC to secondary and Second Chance schools.

For this purpose, after a wide literature review, the project will organize data collection phase at schools using in-depth interviews, life histories, focus groups, school ethnographies and data surveys. Finally, an implementation phase will take place giving participants the opportunity to explore project's tools as: Safe Teaching Training Program, Safe School Label or Safe Learning e-portfolio.

In summary, a multilevel, multistage and intersectional research, exploring different European educational contexts, will be implemented, including 120 schools, 18,000 students, and 2,400

teachers from 6 European countries (Poland, Lithuania, Spain, Italy, Bulgaria and Portugal) in 4 schools' stages, with special attention to multi-disadvantaged learners.

LET'S CARE, supported by an expert consortium, will implement a holistic methodological approach, including cocreation mechanisms, and will translate research findings into political approach, through formulation of novel evidence-based policy recommendations, raising awareness on safe/caring schools, combating social exclusion of disadvantaged learners.

Within the LET'S CARE project, **3 schools per country** (total 18 schools) will participate in the **Community of Schools (CoS)**. This community will meet online, with English as the working language. These 18 schools will be involved in the project's model validation, qualitative data collection and piloting phases. As a result of this participation, Cos members:

- Will be trained in different methodologies related to LET'S CARE concepts and participatory approaches.
- Will be an active part of LET'S CARE resources as Safe Teaching Practices wiki-database, aimed at generating and supporting collaborative dynamics of self and peer observation, and Safe Teaching, in order to improve the safety and care of students in relation with their teachers, offering the possibility of sharing practices and validating peer practices.
- Will have access to Safe Learning e-portfolio tool, a longitudinal student monitor tool, useful for school guidance, orientation and tutorial action to follow up and help the transition process between teachers, schools' stages or schools. This tool will be based on the detection of risk and resilience indicators of Safe Learning, school achievement and engagement.
- Will have access to Safe Teaching Training program, a training program comprised of formative materials adapted to each school stage and focused on the training of teachers and school boards in terms of safety.

From March 2023, **20 schools per country will be selected to participate in the fieldwork** (online questionnaire and ethnographic research to be carried out in schools). To ensure the coordination of schools per country, two coordinators per country will be appointed (12 in total), who will be part of the **National Coordinators Board or NCB**, one of them will be a member of LET'S CARE team, and the other one will be **a teacher selected to represent the national school community of the country**. The NCB will meet online (working language will be English). NCB will be directly involved in different issues, such as select and invite a maximum of 120 schools (20 per country), the project's model

validation or adaptation and implementation of the data collection process. NCB members will be trained during the project in different project tools such as trainer of Safe Teaching Training Program.

The **actions to be developed** are as follows:

In the **2022/23 academic year**:

- One focus group with teachers (5- 7 teachers per school)

In the **2023/2024 academic year**:

- Teachers of focus group will participate in a professional community of practice. They reflect and observe their educational practice to systematize and publish them in the HUB. These teachers will publish and exchange their practices through the HUB and other spaces as journals and conferences.

In the **2024-2025 academic year**:

- 150 students and 20 teachers will participate in a data collection survey.
- (only for Italy, Poland, and Spain) A small pre-test of LET'S CARE tools piloting will be carried out.

In the 2025-2026 academic year:

- (Only in Extremadura) The e-profile tool will be piloted
- (Only for Italy, Poland and Spain) A group of 6-7 teachers per-country will participate in the piloting of the LET'S CARE Teacher Training Program, also with the opportunity to give feedback.
- The school headmaster of 10 schools per country will be trained to use the Safe School Label to check the assessment checklist and give feedback.